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The Impact of Social Media Use on Children's Mental Health

Abstract

Self-image and general mental health are becoming more and more impacted by the growing use of technology in contemporary society. Children's self-esteem is often harmed by the examples and content they see on social media, which raises their risk of anxiety, depression, stress, and emotional regulation issues. This paper examines the effects of social media on teenage mental health, with a focus on how it affects stress management, anxiety, and depression.

Introduction

A child's mental health is a critical focus area since the brain is actively undergoing constant development, which makes it susceptible to mental health issues. When this ongoing development is hindered, it could have long-term consequences for social relationships and academic performance. [It's important to understand that one in seven 10-19-year-olds experiences a mental health disorder that accounts for 15% of the global burden of disease in this age group](#)(World Health Organization,2023). Considering the amount of social media use among

children, around 95% of youth from the age of 13-17 use social media constantly(NIH), an important question arises: how does social media affect adolescent mental health, and what can be done to prevent potential negative outcomes?

Methods

To ensure a comprehensive and reliable synthesis of the best available information, this paper utilized the principles of a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). This organized approach allowed for an unbiased investigation into the relationship between social media use and adolescent mental health. The ultimate goal was to provide a complete and reliable summary of the current evidence. The foundation for organizing the findings was based on the methodological approach used in the established review by Keles, McCrae, and Grealish (2019), which demonstrated that focusing on the type of use is more informative than focusing only on the total time spent.

Search Strategy

The research focused on three major online databases that house professional medical and psychological research: PsycINFO, Google Scholar, and PubMed (MEDLINE). The search was deliberately restricted to research released in the last ten years, covering the period from January 2015 to October 2025.

The search was performed using three sets of keywords combined to find the appropriate papers:

1. Demographic Terms: "adolescent," "teen," or "youth."

2. Platform Terms: "social media," "Instagram," "TikTok," and "Facebook."
3. Mental Health Terms: "anxiety," "depression," "stress," or "psychological distress."

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Following the initial search, specific criteria were applied to filter the results and select only the most relevant studies:

Type of Publication: Only formal, peer-reviewed research studies were included; opinions, news articles, and blogs were excluded.

Study Group: Studies primarily examining children (under 10) or adults (over 19) were eliminated, as the study group had to concentrate on adolescents (defined as ages 10 to 19).

Relevance: Each study had to directly measure a mental health outcome and social media behavior to ensure it examined the precise relationship under investigation.

Language: Only studies published in English were included.

Data Analysis

The data from the final selection of studies were separated into four primary social media use categories to analyze the findings. This approach allowed for a precise determination of which behaviors are most closely associated with negative effects on mental health:

Time Spent (Duration): This gauged how many hours teens spend on social media each day or how frequently they check the apps to see if spending more time is consistently associated with poorer mental health.

Activity: This examined the type of engagement by contrasting Active Use (posting, chatting, and creating content) with Passive Use (merely scrolling or viewing posts).

Investment: This category studied the amount of emotional energy and self-worth that teenagers place into their online personas (such as giving great thought to likes or their profile) to determine whether excessive emotional investment is more detrimental than infrequent use.

Addiction (Problematic Use): This category included research that assessed compulsive, uncontrollable use that resulted in obvious issues, like withdrawal or sleep loss, to ascertain whether this type of behavior is most strongly associated with mental health issues.

Findings

The systematic review by Keles, McCrae, and Grealish (2019) organized its findings across four domains of social media use (Time, Activity, Investment, and Addiction), concluding that all domains demonstrated some correlation with negative mental health outcomes. The study suggests a clear positive relationship between heavy social media use and anxiety (Tsitsika et al., 2014; Yan et al., 2017). Furthermore, a higher number of social media accounts correlated with increased anxiety, suggesting the overwhelming demand of juggling multiple platforms is a factor (Primack & Escobar-Viera, 2017). The review also noted that increased checking frequency was correlated with anxiety, and that girls and younger adolescents appear more susceptible to difficulties with mental health. (Barry et al., 2017; Discussion).

The relationship with depression was notably more complex, heavily influenced by the type of use rather than mere duration (Keles et al., 2019). Studies focused on Investment and Addiction

showed consistent findings: problematic social media use was correlated with psychological distress, and higher emotional investment was associated with increased depressed mood, which was found to be mediated by factors such as sleep disruption (Marino et al., 2018; Neira & Barber, 2014; Vernon et al., 2017). In terms of Activity, both active and passive use correlated with increased depressed mood, with passive Facebook use specifically shown to predict social comparison and envy that can eventually damage self-esteem and lead to depression (Appel et al., 2016; Frison & Eggermont, 2016). Crucially, some studies contradicted this knowledge, showing that the simple amount of time spent on social media does not consistently correlate with depressed mood (Banjanin et al., 2015). Social media can also offer benefits, providing social support that helps reduce isolation and loneliness (O’Keeffe & Clarke-Pearson, 2011).

Finally, the authors highlight the fundamental limitation of the evidence base: Causality cannot be determined. Since 12 out of 13 included studies were cross-sectional, it is impossible to determine whether social media use causes mental health problems or if individuals with existing issues are more likely to engage problematically (Keles et al., 2019). The authors strongly recommend that future research should use qualitative inquiry and longitudinal cohort studies to explore the mechanisms of effect and establish causation (Abstract and Discussion).

Discussion

The evidence suggests that as adolescents progress, spending time on social media interferes with their neurodevelopment and social well-being. Spending a substantial amount of time on

social media can have complex yet disruptive effects, as frequent use is consistently linked to anxiety and depression (Keles et al, 2019). Constant exposure to social media trends can easily lead to unhealthy social comparison, causing a distorted sense of low self-esteem and contributing to body image issues or eating disorders (Yale Medicine, 2024). The perpetual need to actively check social media can also trigger strong feelings of exclusion and loneliness, a phenomenon commonly known as the “Fear of Missing Out” (FOMO). A teen may feel socially isolated in these online interactions, failing to satisfy the deep human need for authentic, in-person connections (Johns Hopkins Medicine).

Moreover, social media platforms are often hotbeds for cyberbullying and harassment, where rumors easily spread. This severely impacts a teen’s self-esteem, which then leads to anxiety and depression. In real-world cases, this is especially concerning since social media sometimes glamorizes self-harm, disordered eating, or other unhealthy coping mechanisms.

Overall, the relationship between social media and well-being is complex. While studies show clear risks associated with excessive or problematic use, social media can also provide certain benefits for some adolescents, such as offering a space for identity affirmation and social support, particularly for marginalized groups. Ultimately, the effects often depend on the individual's existing vulnerabilities, the specific content they consume, and the degree to which online activity displaces essential healthy behaviors like sleep, physical activity, and in-person interactions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while social media has its benefits, the negative impacts on youth mental health remain stronger. Whether or not you're frequently spending a tedious amount of time on social media, it still influences trends that are connected to glamorizing unhealthy coping skills, such as self-harm and eating disorders. In summary, the evidence confirms that the influence of social media on adolescent mental health is highly complex, primarily depending on the nature of engagement rather than the amount of time spent (Keles et al., 2019). The research consistently demonstrates that the strongest predictors of increased anxiety and depression are problematic behaviors like high emotional investment and addictive use.

Social media indeed offers certain pros, such as providing social support and a space for identity affirmation, particularly for marginalized groups. However, based on the evidence reviewed in this paper, it is clear that these potential benefits do not outweigh the pervasive cons. The continuous cycle of social comparison, feelings of exclusion (FOMO), and direct exposure to content that glamorizes unhealthy coping skills, such as self-harm and eating disorders, contributes directly to elevated rates of anxiety and depression in adolescents.

Though most research cannot definitively prove causality due to the high number of cross-sectional studies (Keles et al., 2019), the strong and consistent correlation between problematic use and poor mental health provides a clear warning. Because adolescent mental health is a developing and highly modifiable factor, these findings emphasize that early intervention and prevention are essential. Therefore, focused public health initiatives, including mandatory digital literacy education for students, parents, and schools, must be prioritized to help our generation navigate the digital world safely. The future well-being of adolescents depends on understanding and proactively managing the psychological toll of social media.

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